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**PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF FORMING WILL-
MAKING QUALITIES OF HIGHER-GRADE STUDENTS IN
PHYSICAL EDUCATION LESSONS**

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ABSTRACT

This scientific article analyzes the pedagogical conditions for the formation of volitional qualities of senior students in physical education classes. The study highlights the pedagogical possibilities of physical education classes in developing such volitional qualities as determination, responsibility, independence, endurance, discipline and goal-setting in students. It also substantiates the effectiveness of using interactive methods, competition elements, team activities and motivational approaches in the lesson process. The article scientifically reveals the educational significance of the pedagogical environment, teacher activity and sports classes in ensuring the physical and spiritual development of senior students.

In the modern education system, the formation of students' personal qualities, especially their willpower, is considered an important pedagogical task. Willpower is a key factor in the development of students' qualities such as self-control, determination, endurance, responsibility, and independent thinking. In particular, physical education classes provide ample opportunities for the formation of these qualities in the process of practical activity. World experience shows that the formation of willpower is effectively carried out through sports and physical training. In this regard, countries such as Finland, Japan, Germany, and South Korea have introduced pedagogical models aimed at ensuring the mental and physical harmony of students. Their experience proves that willpower is one of the main psychological and pedagogical factors ensuring the development of the student's personality.

The system of physical education and sports is also undergoing a radical reform in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Law "On Education", the Law "On Youth Policy", and the Presidential Decree "On Comprehensive Measures for the Physical and Spiritual Education of Youth" are taking scientific and practical work in this area to a new level. Creating pedagogical conditions that ensure the development of the willpower of a person, especially in teaching physical education, has become an urgent issue. Today, there are certain contradictions in the formation of willpower in senior students in secondary schools. In particular, pedagogical approaches aimed at developing such qualities as self-control, goal-orientedness, and a sense of responsibility in students are not sufficiently systematized. Despite the fact that physical education classes are a natural and effective means of educating these qualities, their effectiveness in practice remains low.

Therefore, the topic “Pedagogical conditions for the formation of volitional qualities of senior students in physical education classes” is relevant in today's pedagogical practice, which is determined by the need to improve pedagogical mechanisms that ensure the physical development of students, as well as their spiritual and volitional well-being.

Among the priority areas of the reforms being implemented in the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, ensuring the physical, spiritual and volitional well-being of the younger generation occupies an important place. The New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022–2026, as well as the “Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030”, set specific tasks for further popularizing physical education and sports among students and youth, forming a healthy lifestyle, and using innovative educational technologies in the educational process.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, large-scale state programs are being implemented to modernize the education system, develop physical education and sports, and form a healthy lifestyle for young people. In particular, the “Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan” identifies the physical and spiritual upbringing of the younger generation, increasing their interest in sports, and strengthening their willpower as one of the priority areas of state policy.

The presidential decrees “On measures for the further development of physical education and sports”, the “National Program for Raising a Healthy Generation” and the “Concept for the Development of Youth Policy until 2025” are directly consistent with the goals and objectives of this study. These documents indicate that, along with the physical training of young people, the formation of their will, determination, and responsible attitude to life is an integral part of the pedagogical process.

Also, based on the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 in 2019-2023, it is planned to modernize pedagogical activities in educational institutions, organize the educational process based on innovative technologies, and expand scientific research in the field of physical education.

The issue of forming students' willpower in physical education classes is one of the current scientific directions in pedagogical science. Although various approaches have been put forward in this direction by domestic and foreign scientists, the pedagogical conditions for the formation of willpower in the process of physical education classes have not been fully systematized.

The scientific research of Uzbek scientists A.Karimov, D.Tursunov, N.Abdullaeva, Sh.Tursunmetov, M.Rasulova, R.Mamajonov studied the problems of forming students' physical fitness, movement culture, and moral-volitional qualities. Although their research highlighted the educational significance of willpower, the pedagogical conditions necessary for the effective organization of this process have not been fully developed in practice.

The works of foreign researchers J. Dewey, P. Lang, K. Rogers, E. Fromm, G. Allport, A. Maslow, L. Kohlberg, M. Han and S. Phillips are aimed at analyzing the importance of the volitional factor in personal development, methods of its education, and mechanisms of self-control in personal activity. Their scientific conclusions prove that sports, movement and competitive environments play a significant role in the process of educating the will.

Nevertheless, although there are theoretical foundations in local studies on the formation of students' volitional qualities in physical education classes, practical mechanisms, diagnostic tools, and pedagogical models remain unsystematized.

Expected scientific innovations:

Pedagogical conditions that ensure the formation of volitional qualities of senior students in physical education lessons will be determined, their effectiveness will be scientifically substantiated and confirmed through experimental work;

A theoretical model of the physical education process aimed at developing volitional qualities in students will be developed, in which the content of the lesson, methodological approaches and integrative mechanisms of teacher activity will be systematized;

A set of diagnostic criteria and indicators for assessing the level of formation of volitional qualities will be developed and adapted for use in practice;

Based on the research results, the practical significance of the pedagogical model aimed at the formation of volitional qualities in physical education lessons will be determined and scientifically based proposals will be made for its implementation in secondary educational institutions.

The results of the research will be of practical importance in increasing the effectiveness of physical education lessons, developing the volitional qualities of students, and improving the methodological activities of teachers. Methodological recommendations, pedagogical models and diagnostic criteria developed on the basis of the obtained scientific results can be used in organizing physical education lessons in secondary schools.

The results of the study can be used in professional development courses for teachers, in the educational process of students studying in the direction of physical education, as well as in pedagogical practice programs.

Through this scientific work, effective ways of forming volitional qualities in students are identified and the pedagogical conditions necessary for organizing this process are systematized. As a result, pedagogical mechanisms that serve the formation of qualities such as self-control, determination, endurance and responsibility in students are put into practice.

The results of the study can be used in the development of educational and methodological manuals, scientific articles and special courses, as well as in enriching the subject of physical education based on modern pedagogical approaches.

In conclusion, physical education classes are one of the effective pedagogical tools for forming volitional qualities in high school students. During the study, the importance of physical education in developing qualities such as determination, endurance, responsibility, self-control and goal-orientedness in students was scientifically and theoretically substantiated. It was also found that the systematic organization of pedagogical conditions, innovative methodological approaches and effective pedagogical mechanisms necessary for the formation of volitional qualities in the process of physical education is important.

The results of the study showed that through the purposeful organization of physical education classes, it is possible to develop not only the physical fitness of students, but also their mental and volitional well-being. At the same time, the implementation of a pedagogical model, diagnostic criteria and methodological recommendations aimed at the formation of volitional qualities will serve to increase the effectiveness of physical education in secondary schools.

References:

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasining “Jismoniy tarbiya va sport to‘g‘risida”gi Qonuni. Toshkent.
2. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining sportni rivojlantirishga oid farmon va qarorlari.
3. Abzalov R.A., Yaruskin R.X. Jismoniy ta’lim insonni hayotga tayyorlashning ijtimoiy instituti sifatida (jismoniy madaniyat vositalari orqali) // Jismoniy madaniyat nazariyasi va amaliyoti. -1993. -№7.
4. Abulxanova-Slavskaya K.A. Shaxsning hayot faoliyati jarayonida rivojlanishi // Shaxsni shakllantirish va rivojlantirish psixologiyasi. – Moskva: Nauka, 1981.
5. Ageyevets V.I., Vydrin V.M. Sportning shaxsning intellektual, axloqiy sifatleri va ijtimoiy faolligini tarbiyalashga ta’siri // Zamonaviy jamiyatda sport. – Moskva, 1980.
6. Ulaboyevich, B. G. (2023). Increasing the Efficiency of the Methodology of Conducting Physical Education Lessons for Students of Grades 5-9 in Hot Climate Conditions. Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education, 2(4), 137-140.
7. Berdiyev, G. U. (2026). Jismoniy tarbiya darslarini ochiq havoda o‘tkazishda issiq iqlim sharoitining mashg‘ulot o‘zlashtirish samaradorligiga ta’siri. Fan-Sportga, (1), 83-88.
8. Ulaboyevich, B. G. (2025). The Impact Of Hot Weather Conditions On The Efficiency Of Lesson Assessment During Outdoor Physical Education Lessons. Stanford Database Library of American Journal of Applied Science and Technology, 5(12), 46-55.

9. Ulobaevich, B. G. A. (2022). Natural Health Instructions in Organizing the Daily Life of School Students Efficiency of Use Reasonable Use in Physical Education. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 177-179.
10. Rakhimova, G., Khashimov, A., Aripov, B., Aglamov, T., Bobokulov, C., Yakhyaeva, K., ... & Ibrokhimova, N. (2025). Application of Calcium Phosphate Nanoparticles Incorporated on Chitosan-Carbon Nanotubes (CaP@ CS-CNT) for Investigation of Physicochemical and Mechanical of Bone Cement. *Journal of Nanostructures*, 15(4), 2170-2182.
11. Sadridin, P., Akhtam, R., Mahbuba, A., Sherzod, K., Gulnora, R., Orif, N., ... & Dilshod, D. (2025). Dual-ligand liposomes nano carrier with Cisplatin and anti-PD-L1 siRNA in head and neck squamous cell carcinoma: a review. *Journal of Nanostructures*, 15(1), 292-300.
12. Urolovich, B. C., & Dilshodbek, K. (2024). Technology of Using Movement Games to Increase the Efficiency of Physical Education Lessons. *International Journal of Scientific Trends*, 3(11), 44-48.
13. Urolovich, B. C. (2023). Pedagogical Principles of Using Activity and National Games in the Physical Education of Student Girls. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(12), 575-579.
14. Bekmurodovich, K. K., & Urolovich, B. C. (2026). FORMING LOGICAL THINKING IN ELEMENTARY STUDENTS THROUGH THE USE OF CHESS IN COURSE AND EXTRA-COURSE ACTIVITIES. *Eureka Journal of Education & Learning Technologies*, 2(2), 39-50.
15. Boboqulov, C. Boshlang 'ich Sinf O 'quvchilarining Aqliy Qobiliyatini Shakllantirishda Dars Va Darsdan Tashqari Mashg 'ulotlarda Shaxmat O 'yinidan Foydalanish Imkoniyatlar. *Maktabgacha va Maktab Ta'limi Jurnali*, 676643.
16. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining aqliy qobiliyatini shakllantirishda dars va darsdan tashqari mashg'ulotlarda shaxmat o'yinidan foydalanish imkoniyatlar. (2026). *MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI JURNALI*, 4(1).
17. Onlayn shaxmat platformalarining boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari tafakkuriga ta'siri. (2026). *MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI JURNALI*, 4(3).
1. *T*, 4(1).